

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)
Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication
ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060
Publisher: Binas Publishing
Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

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“THE THREAD UNSPUN”

Our brother, twenty-six years to the sun,
His life thread abruptly came to be.
A ship that sails when its long task is done,
He eases beyond the turbulent sea.

His laughter always bright and beaming,
Echoes through walls of consciousness.
A soul unencumbered, no longer binding
A gentle soul, a treasure we now witness.

Though sorrow lingers, intense in anguish,
We know his heart has not truly fled.
Just as wisdom sprouts and establish,
His earnest life's thread unspun, instead.

Life and death are interwoven and wreathed,
A tapestry of moments, gloomy and glaring.
He is not lost, but has merely unsheathed.
A beacon in the dark, no longer despairing.